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**ISSUES AND CONCERNS ENCOUNTERED BY ELEMENTARY TEACHERS IN
TEACHING INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY IN SCHOOLS IN
ZONE 2 OF INFANTA DISTRICT: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION PROGRAM**

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the issues and concerns of elementary teachers in integrating ICT in teaching among selected schools in Zone 2. The results of the study served as the basis for designing the best intervention program. The overall weighted mean of issues encountered by elementary teachers in schools in integrating ICT was verbally interpreted as partially. It showed that most of the teacher-respondents considered producing a text using a word processing program as one with “a lot” of concern. Concerns of teachers in integrating ICT skills in teaching are partially observed and agreed upon by the elementary teachers in Zone 2. The teacher-respondents strongly agreed that the intervention programs for teacher-respondents in ICT integration are most needed in their field. Based on the data gathered, an insufficient number of computers played much to various issues among elementary teachers in integrating ICT into teaching style. Due to limited computers in school and at home, teachers still lack of skills in using or integrating ICT in their teaching style, which also upset the learning process. Computers must be sufficient for simultaneous practice and usage during the integration of ICT in teaching; usual hands-on for all learners is a must. Teachers are recommended to enhance their professional skills in handling or using computers during the integration of ICT in teaching style.

Keywords: *classroom Instructions, issues and concerns encountered, ICT, Classroom Integration, Intervention Program*

INTRODUCTION

Technology is transforming the way people live their lives. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has brought profound change to almost every aspect of people's lives in recent years and this change is nowhere more evident in classroom settings and learning instructions. Information and Communication Technology in education can be used to enhance, enrich, and extend learners' learning in school. It can transform teaching and learning when deployed appropriately and substantially-changing the traditional classroom to where the students learn collaboratively and construct knowledge for themselves. Learning is facilitated dramatically by Information and Communication Technology in ways that were not possible in the past.

Access to Information and Communication Technology prepares learners for living in a rapidly changing society and prepares them for employment in technologically esteemed occupations. Technological skills have become the basis for living a full life as being able to read, write, and compute. Apart from being an engine of sustainable economic growth, technological skills are at the heart of a more cohesive, more equal, and successful society. As part of this, schools and other educational institutions are supposed to prepare students to live in a knowledge society and to consider Information and Communication Technology in the curriculum.

Department Order 78, s. 2010, Guidelines on the Implementation of the Department of Education (DepEd) Computerization Program (DCP), aims to provide public schools with appropriate technologies that would enhance the teaching-learning process and meet the challenges of the 21st century. This program responds to the computer backlog of public schools by providing them with hardware and software and training on simple troubleshooting. This is the government's initiative to promote tech-savveness in rural villages and remote-area schools.

In line with the K to 12 Curriculum, programs, and goals of making every child a globally competitive learner the Department of Education issues DO.1 s, 2007, strengthening the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Governance of the Department of Education. This guideline promotes the use of Information and Communication Technology to support the teaching and learning process in the classroom.

In conjunction with preparing the students for the current digital era and globalization, teachers are seen as the key players in using Information and Communication Technology in their daily classroom instruction. It offers many tools that can be used in the classroom to improve teaching and learning quality.

According to Gupta and Gupta (2014), ICT not only helps to avail the depth of knowledge of the basic courses but also increases the flexibility of delivery of education so that the learners can easily access knowledge. Information and Communication

Technology can influence the way students are taught and how they learn the processes that the learners do not the teachers. Teachers will play an effective role in the overall use of Information and Communication Technology; their main task will not be to transmit information and culture but rather to act as experts to motivate learning.

Information and Communication Technology integration is the process of determining where or how technology fits in the teaching and learning scenarios. It enables everyone to enter the websites from anywhere at any time to use the free information given by the internet. Worldwide research has shown that Information and Communication Technology can lead to improved student learning and better pedagogical practices as well.

Meanwhile, Rouse (2010) said that through ICT integration, the learners can have a virtual learning environment. It is the basic component of a virtual classroom where the teaching and learning environment is located within a computer-mediation communication. It is just like in a real-world classroom; the students in a virtual classroom participate in instruction, which means that the students are logged into the virtual learning environment at the same time.

With this study, the researcher aims to identify the problems and challenges encountered by elementary teachers in teaching with ICT in schools which can help conduct and formulate possible and effective solutions for those particular problems. It also aims to determine the challenges of using ICT tools in teaching and learning processes among elementary teachers in selected schools in Zone 2 of Infanta District. The researcher further aims to formulate interventions and contingency actions that may be performed to address the issues and concerns. With that, this study can be a beneficial tool to provide quality and valid interventions aligned with the problems, practices, and challenges experienced by the teachers in using and applying information and communication technologies in their teaching and learning style for their learners. It may vary information suited to their needs.

Research Questions

1. What are the issues encountered by elementary teachers in school in integrating Information Communication Technology into their teaching style?
2. What are the concerns of elementary teachers in integrating Information Communication Technology in teaching?
3. What intervention program could be derived from the findings of the results of this study to enhance teacher issues and concerns in integrating ICT in teaching?

METHODOLOGY

This study used the descriptive-quantitative approach in nature employing a quantitative approach. It is descriptive for this research describes “what is”. According to Vargas (2015), it involves the description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the condition that exists. It involves some types of comparison or contrast and attempts to discover the relationships between existing manipulated variables, such as issues and concerns. The process of descriptive research goes beyond mere gathering and

tabulation of data. It involves an element of interpretation of the meaning or significance of what is being described. Thus, descriptive research was employed using quantitative means. This method gave the researcher insights to describe the issues and concerns. It also helped to get appropriate information to identify and determine the answers to the sub-problems of this study.

This study covered Zone 2 of Infanta District to determine issues and concerns of elementary teachers in integrating Information and Communication Technology among Elementary school teachers. It was composed of four elementary schools: Agos-Agos Elementary School, Banugao Elementary School, Lual Elementary School, and PICAB Elementary School. The researcher chose the following schools due to easy access since the researcher is also from the said Zone and a former learner of one of the schools enumerated above. Two of the mentioned schools are small school and two, medium-sized schools. Each school is headed by a full-fledged school head. Most of the schools are close to the national road except Agos-Agos Elementary School, which is the farthest part of the locale.

The data gathered from the dry-run were statistically treated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r). It is a statistical measure of test of reliability for quantitative (interval data) items.

The coefficients of correlation (r) computed for the two groups had a very high relationship which registered significance at the -1.00 level. The coefficient of correlation for the odd items was -0.92 . These results mean that the researcher-designed survey instrument was indeed reliable and valid. Therefore, it was a valid instrument to gather the necessary data. The questionnaire was administered to qualified respondents as actual respondents of the study.

To identify the responses to the issues and concerns in integrating ICT, Weighted Mean was used. It was also used in determining which intervention program would be needed by elementary teachers in Zone 2 of Infanta District.

1. **Weighted Mean** is an average calculated by taking into account not only the frequencies of the values of a variable but also another factor such as variance

RESULTS

Table 1

Weighted Mean and Rank of Issues Encountered by Elementary Teachers in Schools in Integrating ICT

ITEM	WM	VI	Rank
1. Insufficient number of computers	3.80	a lot	1
2. Insufficient number of internet-connected computers	3.46	partially	2
3. Insufficient Internet bandwidth or speed	3.29	partially	4
4. Insufficient number of interactive whiteboards	3.34	partially	3
5. Insufficient number of laptops/notebooks	3.11	partially	5

6. School computers out of date and/or needing repair	2.93	partially	7
7. Lack of adequate skills of teachers	2.75	partially	10.5
8. Insufficient technical support for teachers	3.09	partially	6
9. Insufficient pedagogical support for teachers language	2.89	partially	8
10. Lack of adequate content/material for teaching	2.75	partially	10.5
11. Lack of content in national language	2.43	a little	16
12. Too difficult to integrate ICT use into the curriculum	2.59	partially	14
13. Lack of pedagogical models on how to use ICT for learning	2.86	partially	9
14. School time organization (fixed lesson time, etc.)	2.66	partially	12
15. School space organization (classroom size and furniture, etc)	2.63	partially	13
16. Pressure to prepare students for exams and tests	2.57	partially	15
17. Most teachers not in favor of the use of ICT at school	1.98	a little	18
18. Lack of interest of teachers	1.95	a little	19
19. Using ICT in teaching and learning, not being a goal in our school	1.80	a little	20
20. No or unclear benefit to use ICT for teaching	2.16	a little	17
Average Weighted Mean	2.75	Partially	

Scale:

- 3:50 – 4:00 a lot
- 2:50 – 3:49 partially
- 1:50 – 2:49 a little
- 1:00 – 1:49 Not at all

Table 2

Weighted Mean and Rank of Concerns of Elementary Teachers in Integrating ICT in Teaching

ITEM	WM	VI	Rank
1. Produce a text using a word processing program	3.30	a lot	1
2. Use emails to communicate with others	2.95	partially	7.5
3. Capture and edit digital photos, movies or other images	2.89	partially	9
4. Edit text online containing internet links and images	2.73	partially	13
5. Create a database	2.86	partially	10
6. Create and/or edit a questionnaire online	2.57	partially	17
7. Email a file to someone	3.07	partially	3.5
8. Organize computer files in folders and subfolders	3.07	partially	3.5

9. Use a spreadsheet (e.g., Excel)	3.11	partially	2
10. Use a spreadsheet to plot a graph	2.55	partially	18
11. Create a presentation of lesson with simple animation functions	3.00	partially	5
12. Create a presentation with video or audio clips	2.71	partially	14
13. Participate in a discussion forum on the internet	2.25	a little	20
14. Create and maintain blogs or web sites	2.43	a little	19
15. Participate in social networks	2.95	partially	7.5
16. Download and install software on a computer	2.61	partially	16
17. Download or upload curriculum resources from/to websites or learning platforms for students to use	2.98	partially	6
18. Teach students how to behave safely online	2.82	partially	11
19. Teach students how to behave ethically online	2.80	partially	12
20. Prepare materials to use with an interactive whiteboard	2.70	partially	15
Average Weighted Mean	2.82	Partially	

Scale:

- 3:50 – 4:00 a lot
- 2:50 – 3:49 partially
- 1:50 – 2:49 a little
- 1:00 – 1:49 Not at all

Table 3

Weighted Mean and Rank of Intervention Program for Elementary Teachers in ICT Integration

ITEMS	WM	VI	Rank
1. Conduct Basic Computer Literacy Program for teachers	3.79	strongly agree	1
2. Mentoring of teacher who are computer-literate to untrained teacher	3.73	strongly agree	4
3. Implementing SSP Program concerning ICT	3.54	strongly agree	9
4. Integrate ICT during LAC sessions	3.75	strongly agree	2.5
5. Once-a-week ICT drill	3.61	strongly agree	8
6. Pedagogical design that integrates ICT in teaching and learning process	3.68	strongly agree	6
7. School – LGU partnership	3.52	strongly agree	10
8. DepEd allocation of fund for ICT program	3.66	strongly agree	7
9. DepEd curricular strengthening	3.70	strongly agree	5

10. Workshop, Seminar, and Training	3.75	strongly agree	2.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.67	strongly agree	

Scale:

- 3:50 – 4:00 strongly agree
- 2:50 – 3:49 agree
- 1:50 – 2:49 disagree
- 1:00 – 1:49 strongly disagree

DISCUSSION

The overall weighted mean in Table 1 which is about the issues encountered by elementary teachers in school in integrating Information and Communication Technology, is 2.75, with the verbal interpretation of “partially”. This shows how teachers in Zone 2 are affected by these issues. As item 1 shows, an insufficient number of computers, rank 1. Though DepEd Computerization Program (DCP) is continuously improving nationwide, it is still a must for teachers to have a sufficient number of computers. As Mikis stated in NAT 1998 there were 10% of the learners who had internet access, of those 25% with computers at home; the teacher’s responses obtained 3.80, a lot. Item 2, insufficient number of internet-connected computers, got 3.46 which ranked 2. Also, item 4, insufficient numbers of interactive whiteboard, 3.34, and item 3, insufficient internet bandwidth speeds, 3.29 these items ranked 3 and 4 respectively, both with a verbal interpretation of “partially”. Meanwhile, items 5, 8, 6, 9, and 16 were marked as partially and ranked 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 respectively. The following item got 3.11, insufficient number of laptops/notebooks; 3.09 for insufficient technical support for teachers; 2.93 for school computers are out of date/or needing repairs; 2.89 for insufficient pedagogical support for teachers; and 2.86 for lack of pedagogical model on how to use ICT in teachings.

There are 2 items that have the same percentage which is 2.75, interpreted as partially; item 7, lack of adequate skills of teachers, and item number 10, lack of adequate content/teaching materials for teaching, and these items both ranked 10.5. As stated in Mikis (2015) in In Retrospect is that ICT did not exist as a separate subject; students learned how to handle computers either in special study groups or through facultative lessons in which the teacher often studied along with the rest of the class which the computer emerged as a teaching aid or tool in other lessons as well. Along with these responses, teachers are not completely aware of the importance of using ICT integration in teaching.

Table 2 presents the computed result of the data gathered aligned with the concerns of elementary teachers in integrating ICT in teaching. “Produce a text using a word processing program” ranked 1 with a computed weighted mean of 3.30 and interpreted as “a lot” of concern. Ranked 2, “Use a spreadsheet (e.g., Excel)”, interpreted as “partially” concern got a computed mean of 3.11; while statement number 7, and 8 ranked 3.5 with a computed weighted mean of 3.07 and interpreted as “partially”: “Email

a file to someone” and “Organize computer files in folders and subfolders”. “Create a presentation of the lesson with simple animation functions” ranked 5, interpreted as “partially”, obtained a computed mean of 3.00. “Download or upload curriculum resources from/to websites or learning platforms for students to use” ranked 6 with a computed mean of 2.98 and interpreted as “partially” a concern. Meanwhile, statements numbers 2 and 15 ranked 7.5, interpreted as “partially” a concern based on the computed weighted mean of 2.98; these state the following “Use emails to communicate with others” and “Participate in social networks”. On the other hand, statement numbers 3, 5, 18, 19, 4, 12, 11, 16, 6, and 10 are respectively ranked as 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, and 18; these are interpreted as “partially” concerns, based on the computed weighted mean of 2.89, 2.86, 2.82, 2.80, 2.73, 2.71, 2.70, 2.61, 2.57, and 2.55. The following statement is stated respectively based on the rank, “Capture and edit digital photos, movies or other images”, “Create a database”, “Teach students how to behave safely online”, “Teach students how to behave ethically online”, “Edit text online containing internet links and images”, “Create a presentation with video or audio clips”, “Prepare materials to use with an interactive whiteboard”, “Download and install software on a computer”, “Create and/or edit a questionnaire online”, and “Use a spreadsheet to plot a graph”. Only 2 statements are considered as “little” concerns, based on the responses, of the teacher-respondents stating the following: “Create and maintain blogs or websites”, and “Participate in a discussion forum on the internet”, with computed weighted means of 2.95 and 2.61 respectively. It shows that most of the teacher respondents considered “produce a text using a word processing program” as “a lot” of concern. Concerns of teachers in integrating ICT skills in teaching are partially observed and agreed upon by elementary teachers in Zone 2. They are of so much concern about producing a text using a word processing program only. Using spreadsheets is somewhat their concern. To seem not aware of excel usage in various computations, emailing a file to someone, and organizing computer files in folders and subfolders, are also moderate concerns of teachers.

Table 3 presents the data on the responses of the teacher-respondents regarding the intervention program for elementary teachers in ICT integration. “Conduct Basic Computer Literacy Program for teacher” ranked 1, with 3.79 computed weighted mean and interpreted as strongly agree. Statement numbers 4 and 10 ranked 2.5, “Integrate ICT during LAC sessions”, and “Workshop, Seminar, and Training”, with 3.75 weighted means and interpreted as strongly agree. Teacher-respondents strongly agree that “Mentoring of teachers who are computer literate to untrained teachers” must be one of the intervention programs based on the computed weighted mean of 3.73. Meanwhile, “DepEd curricular strengthening” ranked 5, with verbal interpretation of strongly agree, based on a 3.70 weighted mean. Ranked 6, “Pedagogical design that integrates ICT in teaching and learning process” with verbal interpretation of strongly agree, got a 3.68 weighted mean. “DepEd allocation of fund for ICT program” ranked 7, with the verbal interpretation of strongly agree, based on a 3.66 weighted mean. “Once-a-week ICT drill”, ranked 8, with the verbal interpretation of strongly agree based on a 3.61 weighted means. “Implementing SSP Program concerning ICT”, with the verbal interpretation of strongly agree, got a 3.54 weighted mean. “School–LGU partnership” ranked 10 with verbal interpretation of strongly agree based on 3.70 weighted means. Based on the total weighted computed mean of 3.67, the teacher-respondents strongly agree that the

intervention program for teacher-respondents in ICT integration is most needed in their field. In this table, an overall positive impression of the listed interventions is strongly agreed by the respondents. It affirms that they are positive to any changes and accept new solutions to cope with issues and concerns enveloping their potential as professionals.

Table 4

The Proposed Intervention Program Scheme

Item	Specific Objective	Strategy	Persons Involved	Materials needed	Time Frame	Expected Output
Issues and concerns	To enhance computer literacy of teachers	Conduct basic computer literacy seminar, workshop and training	ICT Coordinator, Teachers and School Heads	Laptop, LCD projector, manuals	October and May	Enhanced basic computer literacy of teachers.
	To implement School-to-School Partnership Program (SSP) concerning ICT integration	Once-a-month activity for ICT enhancement program	Teachers and School Heads	Handbook, ICT tools	Year-Round	Implemented the School-to-School Partnership Program (SSP) concerning ICT integration
	To train teachers who are not computer literate	Peer Coaching Once-a-week ICT drill	ICT coordinator, Teachers	Laptop, Desktops, Manual	Once a month	Trained teachers who are computer literate
	To improve pedagogical design that integrates ICT in teaching and	LAC sessions, conduct action research and research	School Heads, teachers	ICT Tools	Year-round	Improved pedagogical design that integrates ICT in teaching and

	learning process					learning process.
	To strengthen DepEd curricular ICT integration	Strengthen Deped curricular through ICT utilization reading activity	School Heads, ICT coordinator and teachers	Manuals, ICT tools, books	Year-round	Strengthened DepEd curricular ICT integration

Research Question 1: What are the issues encountered by elementary teachers in school in integrating Information Communication Technology into their teaching style?

The overall weighted mean in Table 1 which is on issues encountered by elementary teachers in school in integrating Information and Communication Technology is 2.75 with the verbal interpretation of “partially”. This shows how teachers in Zone are affected by said issues. As item 1 shows, the insufficient number of computers ranked 1; though DPC is continuously improving nationwide it is still a must for teachers to have a sufficient number of computers.

Research Question 2: What are the concerns of elementary teachers in integrating Information Communication Technology in teaching?

It shows that most of the teacher respondents considered “produce a text using a word processing program” as “a lot” of concern. Concerns of teachers in integrating ICT skills in teaching are partially observed and agreed by elementary teachers in Zone 2; they are so much concerned about producing a text using a word processing program only. Using spreadsheets is somewhat their concern. It seems that they are not aware of the excel usage in various computation. To email a file to someone and to organize computer files in folders and subfolders are also moderately concerns of teachers.

Research Question 3: What intervention program could be derived from the findings of this study to enhance teachers’ issues and concerns in integrating ICT in teaching?

Based on the total weighted computed mean 3.67, the teacher-respondents strongly agree that the intervention programs for teacher-respondents in ICT integration are most needed in their field. An over-all positive impression to listed interventions is strongly agreed by the respondents. It affirms that they are positive to any changes and to accept new solutions to cope up with issues and concerns enveloping their potentials as professionals.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The Insufficient number of computers played much in various issues of elementary teachers integrating ICT into teaching style. Due to limited computers in school and at home, teachers still lack skills in using or integrating ICT into their teaching style which also upsets the learning process. The significant advantages of ICT are interactivity, immediate feedback, infinite patience, variable levels of difficulty, and motivation. These concepts and theories proved that ICT is powerful in presenting and representing information in different ways specifically in teaching and learning. It also provides strategies and techniques on how to use ICT effectively. Teachers' actions largely influence their students' achievement.
2. It showed that most of the teacher respondents considered producing a text using a word processing program as a lot of concern. Concerns of teachers in integrating ICT skills in teaching are partially observed and agreed upon by elementary teachers in Zone 3.
3. They are so much concerned about producing a text using a word processing program only. Using spreadsheets is somewhat their concern. They seem to be moderately unaware of Excel usage in various computations, emailing a file to someone, and organizing computer files in folders and subfolders were also moderately concerns of teachers. The types of teachers who use technology, how that technology is used to alter teaching practice, the effects on collegial relationships, and the stage of integration that the teachers process through when adopting technology as a part of their teaching are areas of recent investigation.
4. Based on the total weighted computed mean of 3.67, the teacher-respondent strongly agreed that the intervention programs for teacher-respondents in ICT integration are most needed in their field. An overall positive impression to the listed interventions is strongly agreed by the respondents. It affirms that they are positive to any changes, accept new solutions, and cope up with issues and concerns enveloping their potential as professionals.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the aforesaid findings and conclusions, the following are highly recommended:

The Teachers

- a. Prioritize the sufficiency of computers in school.
- b. Computers must be sufficient for simultaneous practice and usage during the integration of ICT in teaching; usual hands-on for all learners is a must.
- c. Enhance their professional skills in handling or using computers during integration of ICT in teaching style.
- d. Undergo various enhancements of information technology skills.
- e. Help or assist school heads in the maintenance and upgrading of computer units that are available in school.

School Heads/Administrators

- a. Design appropriate interventions as needed by teachers.
- b. Evaluate teachers' capability and skills in using and integrating ICT in teaching.
- c. Conduct regular Learning Action Cell sessions on various ICT intervention programs that must be implemented and sustained.

Department of Education

- a. Enhance teachers' skills in ICT integration in the teaching-learning process.
- b. Strengthen and expand ICT curricular requirements to accommodate widespread applications in the teaching-learning process.

External Stakeholders

- a. Partake in school endeavors in safeguarding and maintaining school properties such as computers.
- b. Extend support in any form for a more committed implementation of the computerization program.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher secured permission from the school authority before data gathering. The researcher ensured that the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents and their respective accounts would be protected. There was no conflict of interest existing in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided. There was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and the results were used purely for research.

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REFERENCES

DepEd Order 78, s. 2010 Guidelines on the Implementation of Department of Education Computerization Program (DCP)

Gupta and Gupta (2014) Adoption of ICT in a Government Organization in a Developing Country: An Empirical Study. The Journal of Strategic Information Systems, 17, 140-154.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jsis.2007.12.004>

Mikis M.K. (2015). Challenges in the usage and teaching of ICT in Schools

Rouse (2010) Towards Improving Distance Education in Nigeria with Virtual Technology. Interlink Continental Journal of Education Research 2016 – academia.edu

Vargas (2015) Research Methodology Strategies Management. JPAIR Multidisciplinary Research 7 DOI.107719/jpair.v7i1.163